

Research

The Construction Architecture Design Measures in the Quality Design Strategy of the Single-Story Teaching Building

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Abstract: The construction architecture design projects will not only affect the university's education and teaching environment, but also affect the safety of teachers and students in university. At present, in the implementation of infrastructure projects in some schools, there are still many factors affecting the construction architecture design engineering projects, and even some violations of laws and regulations, which expose the shortcomings of the construction supervision mechanism. That is why question arises how to ensure the construction architecture of the teaching building projects and improve the architecture design level of engineering projects is particularly important. This study mainly combines the construction examples of the single-story teaching building project, which first illustrates the relevant theoretical knowledge of project design and project quality design, and finds the main theoretical basis for the research of this topic. Secondly, the overview of the single-story teaching building project is discussed, mainly involving the knowledge of project construction background, project site construction conditions, engineering construction plan and other aspects. Thirdly, it is mainly analyzed, summarized and discussed in combination with the main problems in the project quality design of the single-story teaching building project, mainly involving the quality problems of the construction site and the quality of construction supervision. Finally, the main design measures and experience adopted in the project construction has been proposed learned for the quality design strategy of the single-story teaching building.

Keywords: Single story teaching building, Engineering projects, Architecture design, Quality design strategy

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Introduction

As a pillar industry of society, the construction architecture design of construction projects is a "century-old plan", and the architecture design projects is not only directly related to the realization of the comprehensive benefit goal of the project, but also related to the safety of people's lives and property. Especially for school teaching buildings and other types of engineering projects. At the same time, construction projects such as teaching buildings are usually public

welfare projects, which are beneficial to the country and the people, and only by fundamentally ensuring the quality of project construction.

Architecture means 'the art and science of building with its basic definition and it is discussed in detail [1]. For Sean lally, who is a futurist and the founder of his multidisciplinary design studio, says: "architecture is much more than the building of an object on a site: it is a reinvention of the site itself". For Blair kami, who is an architecture critique and the writer of 'why architecture matters: lessons from Chicago', says: "architecture is not a purely private transaction between architects and clients. It affects everyone, so it ought to be understandable to everyone" [2]. Even these two quotes are enough to explain the complexity of architecture as well as the complexity of expectations from architecture as a discipline, which is, in fact, not a slight combination but a synthesis of disciplines. Therefore, architecture is an interdisciplinary area. It is a world of design, materials, textures, history, culture, art, technology, construction [3], visualization, economics, and management and so on. From the very ancient times to our space-colonization thinking times, architecture display all the creativity and novelty of humankind in building shelters, mansions, temples, tombs, settlements from tribal colonies to modern societies, from landscapes to cityscapes [4]. It is impossible not to wonder about the history and the imagination behind as well as the construction technology made it possible to stand when one sees Taj Mahal or La Sagrada familiar. As per these two examples, a design requires one to have an intellectual knowledge of different areas to be realized. Today, the education of an architecture student is cumbersome; too much to include in a limited period [5]. Although it appears a more focused and a separated discipline, interior architecture/design has also similar problems. Its education needs to establish the link between architecture and interior architecture/design, which can entirely be another topic of another paper, and the link between architecture and further disciplines (e.g., civil, and electrical engineering) [6].

The link between architecture and interior architecture or design includes history, theory and methodology of design, design principles and inspirations, scales from building layouts to furniture design for a building or historical concept etc. The latter link includes understanding the design and its buildability [7], how and why and when a design needs revisions, who takes part in the construction process, how an architect cooperates with other parties etc. [8]. It is not wrong to say that the latter link clarifies the difference between an architect and an interior architect/designer. Hence, this is beyond important to achieve in the very early stage of their education [9]. In universities the academic curriculum of disciplines often includes one or more introductory modules.

Architecture is the result or the product of several sequences and efforts, the combination of many talents and skills, the real manifestation of a real concept [10]. The process of delivering the finished project is simply called 'construction'. Construction and architectural projects are not a series of isolated events [11]. The above explains why architects need to know about the process of construction since it inevitably starts with architecture at first [12]. For an architect, it is necessary to know about building materials, structural designs, site and project and time management [13]. One does not master all of them, but need to have a background enough to anticipate how it is going to be easy or challenging, economically feasible or pushing the budget hard, and so on [14]. Particularly, an architect needs to understand when and why he/she must compromise his/her design due to the engineering systems (e.g., modeling calculations, material and component production and transportation, etc.).

This study focuses on the content development of the module of introduction to architecture and building construction [15], which is delivered to the freshmen of the department of interior architecture and environmental design in their final semester. The module is compulsory to complete single story teaching building and is formed of architecture design [16]. In accordance with the title as well as the structure, the content was developed in two-folds. For the part of introduction to architecture, student was assigned a well-known architect to study, which aimed to make students familiar with the names, their career path, their design approach and building characteristics, the history of movements

they followed, their strands in interior design and product design. For the part of introduction to building construction, it was aimed to make the students familiar with the world-renowned designs as well as materials and construction technology they used.

The main contribution of our study is as follows:

- We have combined the construction of the single-story teaching building project and project quality design, and finds the main theoretical basis for the research of this topic which first illustrates the relevant theoretical knowledge of project design.
- We have given the detail overview of the single-story teaching building project which is discussed briefly, and mainly involving the knowledge of project construction background, project site construction conditions, engineering construction plan and other aspects.
- We have focus and mainly analyzed as well as summarized the combination with the main problems in the project quality design of the single-story teaching building project, mainly involving the quality problems of the construction site and the quality of construction supervision.
- In the end we have given the design measures and experience adopted in the project construction that been learned for the quality design strategy of the single-story teaching building.

The study is categorized as follows: section 2 demonstrates the relevant background study about the quality design approach for single-story teaching buildings. Section 3 debates the structural design methodology and its measures[17]. Section 4 discusses the design procedures as well as debates the challenges with the structural analysis. In section 5 we have given an example of AutoCAD quality design approach for single-story teaching building and its analysis. Finally, the study is concluded in section 6.

Relevant theoretical knowledge of project design

Generally, building is a structure that provides basic shelter for the humans to conduct general activities[18]. In common prose, the purpose of buildings is to provide humans a comfortable working and living space and protected from the extremes of climate. However, a building usage is depending on the lifespan and the change of rate effected on their impact on efficiency of use. Hence, more attention needs to be emphasized on the performance of buildings as the changes are not static over time. This paper highlights the concept and requirements in evaluating building performance. Exploration on the concept of building performance is also addressed on the purposes of building performance and the link of performance towards the end-users and incorporating their feedback. It concludes that obtaining users' feedback is vital in building performance and the requirements of assessment must outline the performance criteria and mandates in such building (see Figure 1).

By utilizing basic scientific developments and the concepts of multiple-criteria decision-making (MCDM), sustainable decision-making within the domains of civil engineering, construction, and building technology may be considerably eased. With an emphasis on published studies that explore the theoretical techniques used to improve the processes of sustainable evaluation and selection within civil engineering, this study aims to offer an overview of the present state of the art. It is important to note that the publications included in this review are only those that can be in the Carafate Analytic Web of Science core collection database. The objective of this study is to carefully examine how papers pertaining to the developments and applications of MCDM have been distributed across different time periods of publication, by the countries and institutions of the authors, and within different journals given our emphasis on multiple-criteria decision-making. In order to provide a thorough study, we looked closely at journal papers from two separate Web of Science categories, namely "engineering civil" and "construction building technology," that were published between 2015 and 2017. These articles have been divided into groups depending on the study areas they cover, the issues they tackle, and the methods they use to make decisions. The research results provided in this review article show a steady

and discernible increase in the use of MCDM techniques, with a particularly substantial uptick seen over the previous three years. The use of MCDM methodologies for promoting sustainable decision-making processes in the fields of civil engineering, construction, and building technology in the United States is confirmed by this trend as having a significant potential and offering good possibilities.

Figure 1 Overall idea and procedure of the quality architecture design

The process for gathering data throughout the design and construction phases and providing it to facility operators is outlined in the Construction Operations Building Information Exchange (COBIE) specification. The traditional method of transmitting copious amounts of paper paperwork to facility operators once construction is complete is revolutionized by COBIE[19]. As a result, there is no longer a need to collect retroactive data on as-built structures, which lowers operational costs. This study gives a general overview of the circumstances surrounding and methods used in the creation and implementation of COBIE. The National Building Information Modeling Standard (NBIMS) Development Team, which oversaw the project, brought in a global panel of specialists, facility operators, construction managers, and asset managers. The requirements analysis that resulted in the creation of a pilot implementation standard, the rules governing the pilot implementation standard, and the creation of an information delivery manual with process maps that make it easier to match user requirements with the Industry Foundation Class model are all fully documented in this report. To reduce the environmental effect of building new structures, we tried to obtain materials locally whenever possible. Particular focus is placed on the method of building as well as the process of choosing the materials, which includes stone masonry using stabilized in-situ earth mortar. Additionally, this work provides recommendations for a more broadly applicable use of this design strategy [20]. In a side-by-side comparison, we assessed how much energy was used to build a single house as opposed to a typical concrete home. We achieved a spectacular reduction in energy consumption of up to 215% as well as a considerable reduction in the environmental effect of transportation of up to 453% by adopting local resources. It's crucial to note, however, that the use of indigenous materials in industrialized

nations might encounter challenges including the disappearance of traditional construction trades and the lack of adequate building standards. In this work, these difficulties are also covered.

1- Structural Design Procedure

It is obvious that architectural team's thorough structural study formed the basis for the single-story teaching building's structural design. The stages listed in figure 1's analysis were as follows:

Figure 2 Detail block diagram of structural design procedure

Design of the Foundation: Using information on the soil and the building's loads, the design team chose the appropriate sort of foundation for the structure. The 1.5 meter thick reinforced concrete raft foundation was chosen by the team because it was made to evenly distribute building loads and avoid settling[21].

Design of the Structural System: The design team chose a reinforced concrete and steel structural system for the structure, which was then optimized to offer the necessary stiffness, strength, and durability. Steel trusses were employed in regions with considerable spans in addition to the reinforced concrete columns, beams, and slabs that made up the structural system[22].

A system of Designing of the Lateral Stability: It is obvious that in order to bear the building's horizontal loads which also including wind and seismic pressures, the design team should have considered and created a lateral stability system. This kind of system has been made up of steel bracing systems and reinforced concrete shear walls that were placed in certain locations to give the necessary stiffness and strength.

Outer Designing of the Building: We have to consider the building envelope during design of exterior of the building, the design team decided on a glass and aluminum curtain wall system that was intended to provide thermal insulation, noise reduction, and natural light and ventilation.

The Sustainable Design: There is a system for the durability and sustainability for the single-story building. By keeping in view these points a team of architects used energy-efficient HVAC, lighting, and ventilation technologies[23], as well as natural light and ventilation, and sustainable materials, in the structural system and envelope of the building.

Structural Procedure and Limitations

The structure's design and construction had certain limitations, despite the thorough design approach and structural analysis used by the design team. The site's constrained area, which limited the building's size and height, was one of the key constraints[24]. Due to this restriction, the structural system of the building has to be optimized in order to offer the needed strength and stability in a constrained space. The Single-story Teaching Building's design technique and structural analysis are crucial steps in ensuring the building's sustainability, use, and safety[25]. Conceptual design, schematic design, detailed design, and construction are a few of the steps that the process encompasses. We will go over

the design process and structural analysis of the one-story teaching facility in this post. Figure 3 in the text below depicts the basic schematic design for a single-story building.

Figure 3 Free body structure design of single storey building

Several phases were included in the structural process for the university's single-story teaching building:

Foundations: To minimize settling or soil collapse, the building's foundation is made of a spread footing system that disperses the weight of the structure across a wide region. Steel columns and beams support the reinforced concrete framework of the building. Shear walls and braced frames are part of the building's lateral stability system, which helps it withstand lateral stresses like wind and earthquakes.

Column Distance: The building's column spacing is constrained by the need for interior space, which can reduce design freedom and make the structural system more complex.

Floor-to-Floor Heights: The floor-to-floor height of a building is constrained by the requirements for ceiling height and can have an impact on the structural design, particularly in high-rise structures. Using computer modeling and analytic techniques, the structural study of the university's single-story teaching facility was carried out to optimize the structural design for the building's functionality, safety, and sustainability. Soil testing, bearing capacity calculations, and settlement analysis were used to assess the foundation to make sure it could hold the weight and stresses of the structure[26].

Structural System analytic: In order to optimize the design for the building's function, safety, and sustainability[27], the structural system was examined utilizing computer modeling and analytic techniques. Column and beam diameters, the need for reinforcement, and connections between parts were all determined through analysis.

Lateral Stability analytic: To make sure the structure could endure lateral loads like wind and earthquakes, the lateral stability system was examined using computer modeling and analytic techniques. The research determined the need for bracing and shear walls as well as the linkages between the parts.

Material Selection: The building's materials were chosen after careful consideration of each type's performance in terms

of structural integrity, robustness, sustainability, and economic viability. Glass and aluminum were chosen for their aesthetic appeal and sustainability, while reinforced concrete and steel were chosen for their strength and long life.

Sustainability Analysis: Using sustainable design techniques including energy-efficient lighting and HVAC systems, the utilization of natural light and ventilation, and the use of sustainable materials, the building's sustainability was examined. The investigation included figuring out how much energy and water the building used, as well as how much carbon dioxide it produced.

Challenges with the Structural Analysis

The structural study of the university's single-story teaching building has a number of drawbacks, such as: sparse data the study was constrained by the lack of data on the loads, material qualities, and site circumstances[28].

Simplifications: The study was founded on stipulations and presumptions that might not accurately reflect the actual circumstances, such as the uniform distribution of loads and the linear behavior of materials.

Human error: The study was susceptible to errors made by humans, such as mistakes made in the input data or the modeling assumptions, which might have a negative impact on the accuracy of the conclusions[29].

Example of the quality design approach for single-story teaching buildings Recognizing and Considering Educational Needs

The university's single-story teaching building is a cutting-edge structure that was created utilizing a thorough design approach and structural analysis. A safe and sustainable learning environment was provided through the building's foundation, structural system, and lateral stability system, all of which were designed to make sure they could take the loads and pressures placed on them. Knowing a facility's function and intended audience is the cornerstone of every high-quality educational structure. Teachers, students, and administrative staff should all be involved in a single-story teaching structure in order to fully understand their individual requirements, preferences, and difficulties as shown in above figure 4. Capacity estimation is the main planning step at this point. What number of classrooms are needed? What other facilities, such as offices, labs, or multipurpose spaces, are necessary? The responses serve as the design's blueprint. However, this plan stresses the superiority of the learning experience rather than just quantity. To minimize distractions, classrooms should be roomy, well-lit, and acoustically sound. The importance of having access to Wi-Fi, charging stations, and digital teaching tools grows as technology is used in education more and more. The layout should be adaptable to many instructional techniques, including standard lectures, group activities, and individual projects.

Setting priorities for sustainability, convenience, along with security

Do not put accessibility and security last; they are essential to good design. Everyone, including those with disabilities, must be able to access every part of the instructional building. Features like ramps, larger entrances, tactile pathways, and specially constructed toilets are examples of how inclusiveness is demonstrated.

Another crucial aspect of preparing for emergencies is having clearly marked, unobstructed emergency exits as well as maybe having spaces designated for providing first aid or medical assistance. As a result of the lessons learned from the COVID period, health considerations today include making sure that there is great ventilation, surfaces that are resistant to microbial development, and areas that provide social isolation when necessary. A top-notch teaching facility design also integrates sustainability in addition to these practical features. Architects may take use of nature by researching the site's environmental context, such as the sun path, wind direction, and regional climate. In addition to lowering the building's carbon footprint, energy-efficient windows, solar energy use, rainwater collection, and green roofing all result in long-term financial benefits. This sustainability is extended through landscaping, which increases biodiversity and provides covered places for outdoor study or leisure.

Figure 4 AutoCAD design layout of a single story teaching building

Combining aesthetics, functionality, and financial viability

A building is an expression of beauty and symbolism in addition to being largely practical. A educational facility's façade should reflect the institution's ethos, possibly in the form of colors, themes, or architectural design. The interior's color scheme, material selection, and design choices may have a big impact on the learning environment. For example, subtle neutral tones may promote focus, while well-placed splashes of color may inspire original thought. Longevity is assured by durable materials, but choosing them should also take maintenance convenience into account. The educational journey might be made more comprehensive by incorporating art, such as murals or sculptures, which might serve as inspiration. However, the economic effects of every design choice should be considered. A quality design strategy focuses on maximizing value within the allocated budget rather than on luxury. This balance necessitates careful cost estimation to maintain quality while being cost-effective. A staged approach may also be required throughout building of the design, particularly if it is an expansion to an existing educational site. Such phasing guarantees that instruction is not interrupted and that, once the new building is finished, the transfer will be smooth. Feedback loops are extremely helpful, both during the design process with 3D models or mock-ups and after occupancy. They change the building from a fixed structure to a dynamic area that constantly adjusts to best suit its instructional goal.

Conclusion

The quality design approach for single-story teaching buildings includes construction architectural design measures that have a significant impact on how well students and instructors will learn. The success of these educational facilities is largely due to their practical design, careful spatial arrangement, attention to sustainability, and aesthetic components. This research article has emphasized the significance of balancing utility, sustainability, and aesthetics to construct single-story teaching buildings that are effective, ecologically responsible, and culturally meaningful. It has done this through case studies and an investigation of design concepts. A layout and building of single-story teaching buildings will continue to be a crucial component of the development of educational infrastructure as educational institutions continue to change and adapt to changing demands. Architects, designers, and educational institutions may collaborate to build environments that encourage learning, promote sustainability, and enhance the educational experience by

adopting the guidelines and strategies presented in this article. Utilizing AutoCAD and Litzhang software, the novel and recommended design approaches for single-story educational buildings present a philosophy of applying different response modification coefficients for walls and diaphragms. These techniques show that using distinct reduction factors for forecasting force demands is a cautious strategy that results in an overestimation of force needs when applied to a variety of one-story buildings and design approaches. When the isolated periods of walls and diaphragms tightly coincide, an exception happens. It is essential to avoid this situation in big warehouses with flexible frames where the increase in building period may benefit wall forces but dramatically increase diaphragm force demands. The Steel Diaphragm Innovation Initiative, which aims to comprehend the effects of inelastic diaphragm response on the behavior of steel structures, is the bigger initiative that this research is a part of. Future research should expand these discoveries to multi-story structures and evaluate the single-story model's collapse while comparing it to AutoCAD building archetypes.

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